

ISSN: 2456–5474

RNI No. UPBIL/2016/68367

VOL.- X , ISSUE- II March - 2025
Innovation The Research Concept

Narratives of Struggle and Delibration of Myths in Mahasweta Devi's "Draupadi"

Paper Id : 19913 Submission Date : 2025-03-01 Acceptance Date : 2025-03-21 Publication Date : 2025-03-25

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DOI:10.5281/zenodo.15202455

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Monika Kathor

Research Scholar
English Department
Shaheed Mangal Pandey
Govt. Girls Post Graduate
College
Meerut, Uttar Pradesh,
India

Monika Chaudhary

Professor And Head
English Department
Shaheed Mangal Pandey
Govt. Girls Post Graduate
College
Meerut, Uttar Pradesh,
India

Abstract

This paper examines the role of women in revolutionary movements, as depicted in Mahasweta Devi's short story "Draupadi". It questions whether Devi romanticizes the female revolutionary figure or highlights the limitations of counter-state actions. This inquiry leads to an exploration of how nationalism, as represented by the state through the character of Senanayak, is central to the narrative. The restrictions imposed on women by the nation-state are contrasted with issues of female subjectivity, where dominant myths of femininity act as a means to define women's behaviour. The argument posits that during times of nationalist crises, when the nation is most vulnerable, nationalist ideals are rigidly enforced. In these moments, Devi's protagonist is empowered, and her suffering enables her to transcend the constraints of myth. Through this, the mythical figure of Draupadi is reimagined (as Dopdi), creating a counter-narrative where the female body and sexuality become a site of resistance. By choosing the 'Draupadi myth' as a model for the subaltern woman, Devi critiques the politics of myth – how certain myths, like that of 'Sita myth', are elevated, while others, like 'Draupadi's', obscure women's complexities. The protagonist of Devi's story is positioned at the intersection of myth and reality, where extreme and "terrifying" actions are necessary to achieve agency, even if only within the realm of fiction.

Keywords Naxalites, Marginalize, Terrorism, Subaltern, Resistance, Revolutionary, Bourgeois.

Introduction

Mahasweta Devi's work emphasises the importance of politics, arguing that the traditional boundaries of art must be pushed to address real-world political issues. She contends that cultural practices should not be confined to traditional ideas of "art", but instead should challenge these limits in order to address human suffering and the realities of political power. Devi's focus is on the effects of 'realpolitik', particularly on marginalized groups. Her female protagonists represent the limited choices available to women, often shaped by complex social structures. As 'Rajeshwari Sunder Rajan' notes, the "choices" these women make are not truly free, but are instead compromises shaped by societal constraints. For subaltern woman, having any access to choice at all is a rare and exceptional event. Devi's female characters often find themselves unable to act politically, caught in the intersecting forces of class, patriarchy, and nationalism, especially within the context of the Naxalite movement. These women are ensnared by these overlapping systems, which severely restrict their agency.

Objective of study

1. To investigate the contribution of women to revolutionary movements.
2. To examine the limitations placed on women by the nation state are compared with concerns about female subjectivity, where prevailing myths of femininity serve to shape and define women's behaviour.
3. To analyse how "Dopdi" stands at the junction of myth and reality.

Review of Literature

This story, along with numerous other works by Mahasweta Devi, sparks great enthusiasm and fascination among readers and writers. This is evident from the type of reviews this story has received.

Arunima Ray, reviewed this story by saying, “ Dopdi is, not romanticized by Mahasweta..... she is a normal woman who loves her husband and enjoys ordinary and mundane things of life. But she is an intelligent and determined woman who has experienced exploitation and wants to do away with it. She is trained guerrilla fighter and adept at self-concealment”

Cielo G. Festino and Lilim Christina Marins writes, “If women like Draupadi (from Mahabharata) were doubly colonized by patriarchal society and the colonizer, Dopdi is triply colonized, considering that to these two layers of submission a third one should be added, as she is racialized by the upper castes and classes.”

Gayatri Spivak and Festino/Marins, in their analysis of Dopdi’s action, delve into how it resonates with the ancient ‘Drauapdi’ of the ‘Mahabharata’. Spivak says, “It would be a mistake, i think, to read the modern story as a refutation of the ancient. Dopdi is (as heroic as) Draupadi. She is also what Draupadi written into the patriarchal and authoritative sacred text as proof of male power- could not be” and Festino/Marins notes that , “Dopdi rejects the values of dominant and patriarchal society, which leave the aggressor confused and speechless, and transforms her into a superior being. She becomes a sign that the police officer is unable to translate. The rewriting of the Indian epic through the recreation of Draupadi as Dopdi can be understood as Mahasweta Devi’s tribute to tribal women”

According to ‘Dhillon’, the exploitation of landless peasants in India, especially in West Bengal, is a longstanding tragedy, as in the history of revolt, from the sanyasis and the indigo farmers to the Naxalbari uprising. In May 1967, a successful peasant revolt broke out in Naxalbari, located in Northern Bengal. This uprising was led by armed revolutionaries affiliated with the communist party of India, who fought against the feudal elite from 1967 to 1972. While the Naxalite movement’s influence was limited to a few regions, its ideology of Naxalism resonated widely and became ingrained in the national consciousness of India. The actions of a marginalized group – rural people taking up arms and defying their oppressors – may seem unimportant to the urban middle class, but they were of great significance to the rural poor. This has led to the oversimplified belief that the Naxalite movement represented a union between peasants and middle-class intellectuals. Over time, however, this historical moment has often been interpreted as a tragedy for the middle class rather than for the peasants, with most analyses focusing on the role of intellectuals, especially young university students, while downplaying the contributions of the rural population. Unlike other peasant movement led by middle-class leaders from Calcutta, the Naxalbari movement was led by an unexpected alliance of peasants and intellectuals. The movement aimed to address the long-standing exploitation of landless peasants and seasonal farm workers, which was maintained through an unofficial alliance between landlords and government authorities, allowing them to easily bypass legal protections. Migrants like Dopdi and her husband Dulna were forced to work for wages below the government’s minimum wage, fighting for their survivals. In response to this unrest, Indira Gandhi’s government stressed the need to strengthen “national identity”, using this as a rationale for suppressing the Naxalite uprising, playing on middle-class fears about the stability of the nation.

Devi’s short story “*Draupadi*” (1988) highlights the class divisions that allowed the central government to secure widespread backing from the elites and middle classes, by emphasizing Dopdi’s lower-class status. This vulnerability is contrasted with the middle-class “gentleman” Senanayak, who takes advantage of it. The story draws attention to the key elements of the Naxalite struggle, focusing on the opposing relationship between the revolutionary and the captor. The Naxalite movement challenges the dominant national narrative established after India’s independence, and the state’s response to the uprising foreshadows the authoritarian measures that would later be seen during the Emergency. In order to quell the movement, the central government deployed military forces, leading to widespread political unrest. The harsh suppression of the Naxalbari Movement, which was referred to as “The People’s Movement”, included act of rape. Sen (2011) also highlights how, in the late 1960s, it was the Naxalites who brought national attention to the sexual exploitation of peasant women in Bengal by their landlords.

The story focuses on the repeated rapes of the protagonist, Dopdi/ Draupadi, shedding light on how political circumstances influence “female” experiences and the shaping of female subjectivity. As Gayatri Spivak writes, “Mahasweta dramatizes the difficult truth : internalized gendering” (xxxviii). Spivak’s focus on the barriers to subaltern speech highlights how the colonial European subject has the power to silence the subaltern. Devi’s narrative emphasizes the dominant postcolonial Indian identity- middle and upper-class, Aryan, and urban- existing within a neo-colonial system that marginalizes and suppresses Adivasi or tribal peoples (Williams 13).

Main Text

“Draupadi” and Reinterpretation of Myth

In “Draupadi”, three main themes regarding gender and nationalism provoke questions about women’s roles in revolutionary movements. My aim is to investigate whether women’s involvement in the revolution, as depicted in the story, is empowering or limiting to their agency. Does Devi glorify the female revolutionary, or does she emphasize the restrictions places on women in counter – state struggles? This question ties into how nationalism is portrayed through the character of Senanayak, who represents the state. The story contrast the limitations imposed on women by the nation – state with the concept of female subjectivity, showing how dominant gender myths shape perceptions of women’s behaviour. The state constructs a unified “national” image, dictating what constitutes “appropriate” gender roles. The intersecting forces of class, caste, and gender establish standards for non-nationalist crises, when the nation is most vulnerable, these national ideals are strictly enforced. In this context, Devi’s protagonist is empowered, and her suffering allows her to break free from the constraints of myth. The mythical figure is reinterpreted to form a counter-narrative that uses the female body and sexuality as tools of resistance. Bloom notes that many have assumed women cannot independently choose to engage in terrorism , often attributing their actions to male influence. This simplistic view, often found in journalistic accounts, overlooks the complexity of women’s participation in such acts.

Draupadi is one of the most renowned heroine in Indian epic. The title of Devi’s short story alludes to an episode in the *Mahabharata*, where Arjuna, the third of the five Pandava brothers, wins Draupadi as a prize after achieving an extraordinary marksmanship feat. When they return home, their mother, Kunti, is unaware of Draupadi’s presence inside the house. Arjuna informs her that he has brought a “gift”, and Kunti, not seeing Draupadi, declares that the gift must be shared equally among all five brothers. Despite the absurdity of sharing one woman among five men, the brothers cannot refuse their mother’s command, leading to Draupadi being forced in a polyandrous marriage. This arrangement is uncomfortable for both Draupadi and the brothers. The eldest brother, Yudhishtira, expresses his dismay, saying, “A woman married to one man is a wife; to two, three, four, or five, she becomes a public woman. She is sinful. Who has ever heard of such a thing?” (*Narayan* 147)

A key turning point in the epic occurs when Yudhishtira loses all his wealth, including Draupadi, to his cousin and adversary, Duryodhana, in a dice game. In a public gathering, Duryodhana attempts to humiliate Draupadi by disrobing her. In response, she calls upon the god Krishna for assistance. Each time Duryodhana pulls at her sari, it miraculously lengthens, preventing her from being exposed. This moment is traditionally seen as a sign of divine intervention, where Krishna rewards Draupadi’s virtue by protecting her dignity through a miraculous act. Spivak argues that “Draupadi’s legitimised pluralisation (as a wife among husbands) in singularity (as a possible mother or harlot) is used to demonstrate male glory. She provides the occasion for a violent transaction between men, the efficient cause of the crucial battle” (183). The restoration of her name’s untainted, mythological form plays a role in an inter-textual strategy (Pesso – Miquel 154). In Devi’s retelling, initially called Dopdi, Draupadi also represents the rebellious tribal woman. The act of naming highlights the intersection of class politics. Draupadi has three names: Draupadi, the “formal” name given by her employer’s affluent wife; Dopdi, the “informal” tribal version; and Upi Mejhen, a name she adopts to disguise herself after her husband’s death. These name symbolize two competing discourses in the narrative: one reflecting the formal language of state and military history, and the other, the informal, daily speech of tribal characters. A deeper analysis of the narrative structure reveals how these discourses reflect ideological positioning. The names are instrumental in shaping the evolution of Dopdi/Draupadi’s identity.

The tribal name cements her position in the underclass, continually reminding her of Draupadi’s enslavement. In the early part of the story, Dopdi’s actions are driven by a mentality of servitude. Even after she leave the service of a household and becomes an outlaw, she is still constrained by the gender and class systems – first through her loyalty to her husband, and later to the elite leaders of the movement. Her devotion to her husband is particularly significant, as it reinforces the link to the Draupadi myth.

On one level, the tribal name shifts attention away from the myth, emphasizing issues of class, ethnicity, and regional identity. It underscores that Draupadi’s name is given to her not out of any true connection, but as an act of generosity from her higher – class mistress. On another level, the name draws a parallel between the tribal woman and the mythic figure, while also reflecting the deep presence of myth in Indian culture and its reinterpretations in the context of contemporary Indian politics. The character of Dopdi/Draupadi does not entirely reject the epic, but it diverges from a faithful replication of the myth. Restoring the pure, mythological version of her name serves an intertextual

purpose: while affirming the status of the iconic polyandrous heroine from the Mahabharata, it also suggests that Devi's modern Draupadi – ravaged and bleeding – bears only a nominal resemblance to her mythological namesake.

Some aspects of the narrative align with the epic. In a significant departure from traditional portrayals of epic heroines like Sita, several versions of *Mahabharata* highlight Draupadi's "dark" complexion. In south Asia, ideals of beauty are often based on factors like skin tone, height, and youthful appearance. A contemporary example of this is seen in the 1993 film *Bhaji on the Beach*, where Jinder, an Asian woman who leaves her abusive husband, is harshly criticized by her mother-in-law as "evil" and blamed for the failure of the marriage and the shame it brings to the family, solely because of her dark skin: "I knew she was no good. Dark girls are shameless."

The emphasis on Draupadi's "darkness" highlights the impact of ideological constructions in the collective consciousness. This may explain why Draupadi is not regarded as the epitome of the "ideal" woman, unlike her counterpart Sita. Frequent references to the "blackness" of Dopdi and her husband create a subversion moment, drawing from the epic while signalling class and caste distinctions that are historically reinforced within hegemonic hierarchies. This also reflects the politics of representation. Myths, like other discourses, remain functional and popular only when they serve the interests of the dominant group. As one of the critic notes, "Myth as an essential source and vehicle of hegemonic control serves to contain and condition the responses of the marginalized 'other', portrayed in Mahasweta's history of the subaltern, which emerges as a dialogue against the oppressive hegemonic Itihas Puranic history of India".

To some extent, the patriarchal foundations of the Draupadi myth are present in Devi's version. Like her epic counterpart, Dopdi is loyal to her husband and continues the struggle out of this loyalty and her promise: "By my life Dulna, by my life. Nothing must be told" (Devi 193). Her connection to her ancestors is rooted in a sense of pride in her "blood", which she believes symbolizes the protection of their women. Interestingly, Dopdi's reference to her "blood" signifies her ethnic purity – her untainted "black" blood – contrasted with Shomai and Bhudna, the traitors in the story, whose blood is "diluted" by American soldiers (Devi 193). The thought "Protected their blood" can be read as implying that her ancestors controlled their sexuality, reflecting one of the Nation's primary anxieties. This becomes ironic because the tribal woman, despite her tribal purity, upholds the dominant ideology of racial purity. The revolutionary's desire to preserve this "dignity" underscores how deeply ingrained this ideology is in the nation's citizens. Devi further exposes the futility of this ideology in the final section of her story. By this point, the revolutionary woman is constrained by societal norms of female behaviour, shaped by the ideals of epic heroines who direct their moral strength and physical energy towards devotion to their husbands. This forms a uniform code of behaviour that erases class, ethnic, and regional distinction.

In the myth, Draupadi's acceptance of her polyandrous marriage is rewarded by Krishna's miraculous intervention. However, in Devi's more realistic portrayal of female subjugation, the absence of any "divine" element is stark. As Spivak correctly points out, Devi does not idealize Dopdi/Draupadi's tribal identity, nor does she overlook the gender and class inequalities that shape the tribal woman's role in the revolutionary movement. Despite the limited political impact of revolutionary politics, the Naxalite movement still provides Dopdi with some active involvement, even if it's just as a messenger. To better understand Devi's perspective on the politics of the struggle within the patriarchal structure of the Indian nation – state, it's helpful to examine the complexities of Dopdi/Draupadi's dedication to the Naxalite movement

When women participate in battle alongside their male counterparts, it is often viewed as assign of gender equality within the movement. However, this perspective overlooks how the mobilization of women in armed conflict can serve as a political tactic that co-opts them into supporting the patriarchal revolutionary agenda, rather than truly liberating them. For example, when a large number of men are killed in battle, women may be recruited to fill the gaps, often becoming expendable pawns in the conflict.

In "Draupadi," there is no attempt to conceal the reality that women are often treated as secondary to male fighters, rather than being active participants in their own right. Dopdi's commitment to the movement is shaped by a male – dominated power structure, and she does not operate independently until her husband's death. To present women's involvement in the Naxalite movement as a recognition of their rights or a step toward "liberatory politics" overlooks the male – centered foundations of the revolutionary ideology. By repeatedly highlighting male voices, leadership, and authority in Devi's story, the narrator critiques the revolutionary rhetoric by emphasizing its phallogocentric nature. The ironic line – "Dopdi felt proud of her forefathers. They stood guard over their women's blood in black armor" (Devi 193) – draws attention to how patriarchal ideas are

appropriated in supposedly progressive movements. The protagonist's sense of identity and dignity is tied to male warrior strength. Similarly, the instructions Dopdi follows and the "voices" in her head are male – controlled. In her introduction to the story, Spivak highlights that Dopdi "keeps her political faith as an act of faith towards (Her husband)" and further argues that the decision – makers among the revolutionaries are always "bourgeois young men and women"(184).

Both the epic and the short story share patriarchal undertones. However, while patriarchal dominance remains unchallenged in the epic, Devi's "Draupadi" ends by subverting traditional gender dynamics, offering a form of resistance. In the story's final moments, Dopdi/Draupadi's act of retaliation against her multiple rapes challenges the patriarchal and nationalist forces that limit female subjectivity. By elevating Dopdi/Draupadi to an epic scale, Devi not only disrupts the dominant myth of divine protection but also highlights "myth's potential to emerge, transform, disintegrate, or disappear entirely" (Barthes 120). In this context, myths holds transformative power – becoming a vehicle for rebellion and granting Dopdi a statue that, even if only briefly, instills fear in her male captors.

" Draupadi stands up. She pours the water down on the ground. Tears her piece of cloth with her teeth. Seeing such strange behaviour, the guard says, she's gone crazy, and runs for orders. He can lead the prisoner out but doesn't know what to do if the prisoner behaves incomprehensibly. Draupadi before him (Senanayak), naked. Thigh and pubic hair matted with dry blood. Two breasts, two wounds..... The object of your search, Dopdi Mejhen. You asked them to make me up, don't you want to see how they made me?. (Devi 196)

The concluding moments of the story raise important questions about female insurgency and resistance to patriarchal and military oppression. These scenes, intended to represent subversion and defiance, challenge the structures of patriarchal and military power and allow for multiple interpretations, one might question whether this highlights the limitations of individual rebellion. Is Dopdi's triumph simply a narrative trick, a singular act of resistance forced upon her by the author, rather than something that can be repeated or applied in a collective context? This uncertainty invites further reflection on whether her act of resistance is genuinely transformative or just a fleeting escape from the entrenched systems of power that continue to dominate her.

After her capture , Dopdi/Draupadi is completely isolated, abandoned by her fellow revolutionaries. There is no male divine figure to restore her dignity or uphold her "respectability", and the male – driven glory that once fuelled her , resolve ultimately fails her. Unlike in traditional epic versions, the narrative does not offer a hopeful or optimistic ending. The only reference to Krishna in Devi's narrative is a parody. This moment exposes the excessive role of religion as a tool for reinforcing patriarchal power. It is the men, especially the state agents, who respond to Krishna's voice, while religion is rendered meaningless, reduced to comedy. This reflects how the Hindu idea of *Shakti*, the female principle, was politically exploited in the anti – colonial struggle, portraying women as capable of great heroism. However, this ideological approach is problematic, as it legitimizes women's involvement in exploitative roles, such as carrying heavy loads for the men, serving them in supporting roles, or being used as decoys.

The portrayal of untiring cruelty that is bestowed upon Draupadi employs two types of imagery. Devi convey the continuous rapes, accompanied by the mutilation of her breasts, by means of animal imagery, which not only strips Draupadi of her humanity, but highlight the animalistic nature that dominates the realm of war. This approach reverses the prevailing power dynamics in the story. When Draupadi acts in an animalistic manner, tearing her cloth with the teeth, it strikes terror into the guards, who are incapable of handling her behaviour. It makes them face the reality of what they've turned her into. Ironically, when Men exhibit animalistic brutality, it is often justified, but Draupadi's own animalistic behaviour is deemed "irrational" because it challenges the expected feminine role of victimhood.

The phrase "Active pistons of flesh rise and fall" (Devi 195) uses mechanical and clinical language, closely linked to military terminology and weaponry. The term "pistons" serves as a euphemism for the penis, symbolizing male domination and playing a key role in Dopdi's victimization. Through this military – style language, the narrative reinforces male authority, state power, and the masculinist character of the nation. Devi's deliberate choice of words highlights the connection between patriarchal systems and state/military discourse. This language eliminates emotional depth, presenting human beings in a detached, clinical manner, akin to military targets. The militarization of language extends beyond the battlefield, influencing everyday life, as seen in processes like sterilization or the systematic elimination of dissenters during the Indian Emergency. The narrative's impact is amplified by the blend of rigid, military language with the casual, everyday

speech of the tribal people. The military discourse is characterized by short, sharp sentences, coupled with the global "language of war" focused on offense and defence (Spivak 185).

The ideological dominance of military language is so deep – rooted that both Dopdi and her captors use this terminology to express profound human suffering. A key example is the term "counter", which serves as a euphemism for "killed by police in an encounter" (Devi 192). Dopdi is haunted by this world, as it becomes ingrained in her mind and influences her every thought and action. When she finally faces Senanayak, she uses this word in her confrontation, and its utterance carries a powerful, almost ritualistic weight. As a subaltern woman, her use of the term underscores the brutality of political and military language. This highlights how language obscures the reality of extreme human suffering. Deaths and disappearance within the state are erased from official narratives through the normalization of such euphemisms.

In this context, the phrase "counter me" also serves as a form of parody. On one hand, it seems absurd because the revolutionary woman is so thoroughly ravaged and stripped of any human dignity that even the prospect of death loses its significance for her (Devi 196). On the other hand, the word "counter" becomes a contradiction, as it fails to accomplish its intended goal. Instead of destroying the subaltern woman, it empowers her. Through her questions, "Are you a man?" and "There isn't a man that I should be ashamed of," she disrupts the masculinity that underpins bourgeois nationalism.

Similarly, the phrase "..... see how they made me" carries multiple layers of meaning. The command to "make her" is akin to the term "counter", functioning as a means to force her to speak. This creates an irony in the light of Spivak famous question, "Can the subaltern speak?". However, Dopdi does "speak", not in a traditional sense, but by tearing her cloth. Her form of expression is not understood because, to the guards, her actions are incomprehensible. Interestingly, Senanayak, who prides himself on being able to predict the revolutionaries' every move, is unable to make sense of Dopdi's actions (Devi 194). As a result, the intent behind his command to "make her" is ultimately unsuccessful.

The word "make" carries the strongest irony in the text. Semantically, it produces the opposite result. Rather than annihilating the revolutionary, it gives rise to her. Rape and torture serve as the primary tools for "creating" a revolution, both functioning as instruments of power and dominance. It is acknowledge that the rape of women reinforces male dominance. This practice has deep historical roots, where the violation of the enemy's women served to solidify territorial and military control. Male identity is intrinsically linked to the notion that rape confirms a woman's possession. Rape, as a specific "sexual form of violence", seeks to appropriate woman as "the sex", objectifying them as "sexualized, eroticized, and devastated bodies". When rape is employed as a tool of patriarchy, it simultaneously reinforces political power. The process of objectifying women is often deeply connected to ideas of masculinity. Although, Senanayak does not engage directly in the rape, his reaction to the news that the tribal woman has been subjugated allows him to vicariously assert his masculine power. The language of war is deeply connected to the language of nationalism, which draws its authority from a masculinised endeavour, where the security of the nation is supported by patriarchal elite structures. While the nation is often portrayed as feminized – 'raped', 'dishonoured', and awaiting rescue by brave soldiers or sons – Devi's narrative shifts this perspective, placing the rapist as 'the state, through its agents – the armed forces, police and intelligence services – who violate their own citizens, those they are meant to protect"

Despite of her tireless rapes, cruelty and intense suffering, Dopdi is "made" in the way that, though horrifically, it liberates her, empowering her, making her heroic, and even legendary. Dopdi's 'making/unmaking' ultimately provokes Senanayak's own downfall. As a result, the confrontation between Dopdi/Draupadi and her captor challenges the prevailing image of nationalism represented by the state, as the woman takes control, and in the moment of violation, it weakens and undermines the language of nationalism. The forced silencing of the subaltern subtext fails. Unlike the boy who silenced himself by biting off his tongue when confronted, Dopdi, from the moment of her capture, disregards even her leader's commands and "ululates with the force of her entire being" (Devi 195). The most striking and tragic part of the story is the image of a violated, broken female body that eventually becomes a pursued, heroic revolutionary.

The change in names, from Draupadi to Dopdi, takes on symbolic significance throughout her process of "making". Devi's use of "making" and "unmaking" places the woman as the active subject, emphasizing her agency. These terms represent ideological and physical shifts where the boundaries between destruction and freedom blur. Dopdi/Draupadi's identity is shaped by the alternating use of her tribal and formal names. In the final part of the story, the name Draupadi connects the revolutionary woman to her epic

counterpart, transforming her into a figure of legendary stature. When she states, "The object of your search Dopdi Mehjen," laughing with bloodied lips and standing defiantly with her hand on her hip, the name "Dopdi Mehjen" – as it appears in her military dossier – becomes a point of ridicule. By naming herself in this way, she reclaims her subjectivity, remaking herself outside the dominant, male – driven language of nationalism and military power.

The moment when "Draupadi pushes Senananyak with her two mangled breasts" stands as the most shockingly assertive act in the story, and for this, Devi grants her the name of an epic heroine (Devi 196). Before delving into Devi's perspective on myth, It's important to note how this moment serves to highlight the core dynamics of revolutionary action for the female revolutionary.

In the final scene, the concept of masculinity, which is essential to supporting the nationalist agenda, is disrupted, and the male gaze can no longer control its usual focus, the female body. Traditionally valued and culturally upheld, the clothed female body is turned on its head, becoming a symbol of rebellion. The story's concluding moments also highlight how female sexuality is conceptualized. Conventional ideas of female sexuality and behaviour are linked to bourgeois morality and dominant nationalism. These ideas raise important questions about agency and female subjectivity.

Traditionally female identity and subjectivity are often tied to the –physical representation of the breasts. Dopdi's nakedness symbolizes resistance from the subaltern against the institutions – such as the state, family, and religion – that define "respectability" and socially prescribed female behaviour. This is compounded by thge imposition of middle – class standards of modesty and respectability, where the ideal woman in modelled to fit the values of middle- class society and is incorporated into the national identity. Dopdi's bold exhibition of her nakedness challenges the relevance of these middle – class ideals, revealing that in the face of conflict, these norms become meaningless. The concept of 'normality' cannot be applied to comprehend Dopdi's trauma

Conclusion

Dopdi's character, in modern interpretations, challenges traditional gender norms and hierarchies. She stands for a rebellion against oppression, particularly the systematic violence against marginalized women in society. Dopdi's actions – her resistance to societal norms and her direct confrontation with violence – reflects the same qualities found in Draupadi's actions in the 'Mahabharata'. Dopdi is a figure that rises above the passive roles often assigned to women in traditional narratives, asserting her agency and autonomy. Dopdi, much like Draupadi, is portrayed as a character who uses her suffering not just as an act of endurance but as a powerful political statement. Both characters are subjected to violation, but their responses turn them into forces for change. Draupadi, through her emotional and spiritual resilience, and Dopdi, through a direct political and rebellious stance, serve as models of defiance against oppressive structures.

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